

Material and Methods, and Supplemental Materials available for The *Arabidopsis* immune receptor EFR increases resistance to the bacterial pathogens *Xanthomonas* and *Xylella* in transgenic sweet orange

Letícia Kuster Mitre^{1,2,*}, Natália Sousa Teixeira-Silva^{1,*}, Katarzyna Rybak³, Diogo Maciel Magalhães^{1,2}, Reinaldo Rodrigues de Souza-Neto^{1,2}, Silke Robatzek³, Cyril Zipfel^{4,5} and Alessandra Alves de Souza¹

¹Centro de Citricultura Sylvio Moreira – IAC, Cordeirópolis, SP, Brazil; ²University of Campinas, Campinas, SP, Brazil; ³LMU Biocenter, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Martinsried, Germany; ⁴Institute of Plant and Microbial Biology and Zürich-Basel Plant Science Center, University of Zürich, Zürich, Switzerland; ⁵The Sainsbury Laboratory, University of East Anglia, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, United Kingdom.

* These authors contributed equally to this work

Material and Methods

Vectors and plant genetic transformation

The binary vector containing the *EFR* gene from *Arabidopsis* was chemically synthesized by the DNA Cloning Service e.K. company (www.dna-cloning.com/). The transgene is under the control of the Figwort Mosaic Virus (FMV) promoter and the *Agrobacterium* nopaline synthase (NOS) terminator. The vector carries kanamycin resistance on the T-DNA, streptomycin/spectinomycin-resistance for bacterial selection, and *gus* reporter gene (Fig. S1).

Agrobacterium-mediated transformation was used to produce citrus transgenic lines as previously described by Caserta *et al.* (2014). Seeds were sampled from mature Valencia sweet orange fruits and cultured in MS/2 solid medium for four weeks in the dark at 27 °C. Seedlings of about 15 cm in length were transferred to a 16-h photoperiod for 15 days and later used as explant source for genetic transformation. Epicotyl segments (0.8 - 1.0 cm) were excised and kept in liquid MS medium supplemented with indole acetic acid (100 mg L⁻¹) before incubation in *A. tumefaciens* (EHA105 strain) suspension (10⁸ CFU mL⁻¹) for 5 minutes. Dried explants were transferred to solid MS co-culture

medium supplemented with sucrose (30 g L⁻¹), benzylaminopurine (BAP) (10 mg L⁻¹), and myo-inositol (100 mg L⁻¹) for three days (24 °C, in the dark). After the co-culture period, the explants were transferred to solid MS selection medium containing kanamycin (100 mg L⁻¹) and cefotaxime (250 mg L⁻¹) for four weeks (28 °C, in the dark) and then retransferred to 16-h photoperiod.

Kanamycin-resistant shoots were excised from the explants and incubated in 2mM X-Gluc solution (37 °C, overnight) for β -glucuronidase (*gus*) assay. Genomic DNA was extracted from leaves using the CTAB method (Doyle and Doyle, 1990) and PCR was performed with the annealing of the forward primers to the FMV promoter (FMV_F) and the reverse primer within the *EFR* sequence (*EFR_R*) (Table S1). The well-developed and PCR positive shoots grown *in vitro* were directly grafted on Rangpur lime (*Citrus limonia*) rootstocks and kept under greenhouse conditions. Source plants were used to produce clones for subsequent evaluations. Transformation efficiency was calculated as the percentage of *gus*-positive shoots in the total of explants exposed to *Agrobacterium* culture.

Nicotiana tabacum was used as an experimental model to assess the role EFR plays in recognizing citrus bacterial PAMPs and its response to *X. fastidiosa* infection. The binary vector pEarlyGate103 containing the open reading frame of *Arabidopsis EFR* was used (Lacombe *et al.*, 2010; Zipfel *et al.*, 2006). Transgenic tobacco was produced by *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation with the strain GV3101, as previously described (Gómez *et al.*, 2020). Vigorous shoots grew in selective media (MS/2 supplemented with 2 μ g mL⁻¹ phosphinothricin) were transferred to pots containing 2:1 substrate/vermiculite and kept in an acclimatization room at 28 °C for 21 days. The presence of the expression cassette 35S::*EFR-GFP-His* was confirmed by PCR using genomic DNA as template and the primers 35S_F and *EFR_R* (Table S1).

EFR copy number

The number of transgenic insertions in *C. sinensis* lines was estimated by qPCR as described by Shepherd *et al.* (2009). The relative quantification was performed using primers at the 35S promoter regulating the NptII selection marker and the lipid transfer protein (LTP, NM_001288873), present in a single copy in the sweet orange genome (Wu and Burns, 2003). Primers are enlisted in Table S1. The primer efficiencies were calculated using LinRegPCR software and the qPCR reactions were conducted as previously described.

ROS production assay

The peptides elf18_{Ec} (ac-SKEKFERTKPHVNVGTIG), elf18_{Xcc} (ac-AKAKFERTKPHVNVGTIG), and elf26_{Xfp} (ac-AQDKFKRTLHVNVGTIGHVDHGKTT) from *Escherichia coli*, *X. citri* and *X. fastidiosa*, respectively, were synthesized by Aminotech Research and Development. Leaf discs (0.5 cm) from young tender leaves were displaced on autoclaved water overnight in a 96-well plate at room temperature and then challenged by 100 µL of elicitation solution (17 mM luminol, 1 µM horseradish peroxidase and 100 nM elf18_{Ec}, elf18_{Xcc} or elf18_{Xfp}). Luminescence was immediately measured over 40 minutes using the Varioskan Flash Multiplate Reader (Thermo Scientific). Assays were performed in triplicates and statistical significance of the means calculated according to Tukey's test (* $p < 0.05$).

For ROS production in response to *X. fastidiosa* bacteria, petioles of six- to seven-week-old *Arabidopsis* Col-0 and *efr-1* mutant plants (Zipfel *et al.*, 2006) were sampled using a scalpel and left overnight in sterile water. The following day the water was replaced with a solution containing 17 µg mL⁻¹ (w/v) luminol (Sigma), 10 µg mL⁻¹ horseradish peroxidase (Sigma) and living *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* Temecula-1 (*Xff*) (Ionescu *et al.*, 2014) cells (OD₆₀₀ 0.125). Luminescence was captured using a TECAN plate reader Infinite® 200 PRO.

Gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR

Total RNA was isolated from leaf tissue of transgenic and non-transgenic plants using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's instructions and treated with RNase free-DNase (Promega). The RNA samples were PCR-tested for genomic DNA cross-contamination. RNA quality and concentration were assessed by gel electrophoresis and spectrophotometry (NanoDrop 8000 - Thermo Scientific). cDNA was synthesized from 1 µg total RNA using High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems) using Oligo(dT)₁₅. The relative expression values were analyzed using the SYBR Prime Script RT-PCR kit (Thermo Scientific) in ABI PRISM 7500 Fast (Applied Biosystems) and were determined by the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). Expression values were normalized by the endogen *cyclophilin* for *C. sinensis* and by the gene *ARPC3* (Actin-related protein C3) for tobacco. The primers used for RT-

qPCR are listed in Table S1. Assays were performed in triplicates and statistical significance of the means calculated according to Tukey's test (* $p < 0.05$).

MAP kinase assay

Leaf discs (0.5 cm) from young tender leaves were displaced on autoclaved water overnight in a 96-well plate at room temperature and were treated with flg22_{Pst} from *Pseudomonas syringae*, elf18_{Ec}, elf18_{Xcc}, elf26_{Xfp}, or water (mock treatment) for 0, 30, and 45 minutes and immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen. The samples were ground into powder before the addition of extraction buffer [50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 100 mM NaCl, 15 mM EGTA, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM NaF, 1 mM Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.5 mM NaVO₃, 30 mM β-glycerophosphate, 0.1 % IGEPAL CA 630, 100 nM calyculin A (CST), 0.5 mM PMSF, 1 % protease inhibitor cocktail (Sigma, P9599) and 5 % glycerol]. The extracts were centrifuged at 16,000 × g and 5x SDS loading buffer added. Protein concentrations were measured by the Bradford assay (Protein Assay Dye Reagent - Bio-Rad) and 30 μg of total protein was separated by 12 % SDS-PAGE and blotted onto PVDF membrane (Bio-Rad). The membranes were blocked in 5 % (w/v) BSA (Sigma) in TBS-Tween (0.1 %) for 1 hour. The activated MAP kinases were detected using anti-p42/44 MAPK primary antibody (1:2500, Cell Signaling Technology, 4370) overnight at 4 °C, followed by anti-rabbit HRP-conjugated secondary antibody (Sigma). Three independent experiments were performed with similar results.

Seedling growth assay

Arabidopsis Col-0, *efr-1* and *bak1-5* mutant seeds were surface-sterilized, sown on MS media supplemented with sucrose, stratified for 2 days at 4 °C in the dark and put in the light. Four days-old seedlings were transferred into liquid MS with or without *Xff*OMVs (see below) and incubated for ten further days. Fresh weight of seven replicates per treatment and genotype was measured using a precision scale and calculated relative to untreated control.

OMVs from *Xff* were isolated as described in Ionescu *et al.* (2014) with some modifications. Briefly, *Xff* was cultured in 100 mL of PD2 medium for seven days. Cells were removed by centrifugation at 10,000 × g for 15 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was filtered through 0.22 μm filter and centrifuged at 38,000 × g for 1 h at 4 °C. The supernatant was removed carefully and subjected to centrifugation at 150,000 × g for 4 h

at 4 °C. The final pellet containing OMVs was resuspended in 1 mM EDTA (pH 8.0) and stored frozen at –80 °C until used.

***Xanthomonas citri* infection assay**

X. citri subsp. *citri* strain 306 (Da Silva *et al.*, 2002) expressing GFP (Rigano *et al.*, 2007) was grown overnight in liquid NBY medium supplemented with ampicillin (100 mg L⁻¹) and gentamicin (5 mg L⁻¹). The bacterial suspension (10⁴ CFU mL⁻¹) was prepared in 1x phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and infiltrated in three regions of three transgenic and non-transgenic fully expanded detached leaves. Citrus canker symptoms were evaluated 7 and 14 days after inoculation (dai). Leaf discs adjacent to the infiltration site were excised to assess the bacterial population from three independent leaves. This assay was performed in triplicates and the statistical significance of the means calculated according to the Student's *t*-test (* *p* < 0.05).

***Xylella fastidiosa* infection assay**

X. fastidiosa subsp. *pauca* (*Xfp*) strain 9a5c (Simpson *et al.*, 2000) was cultivated in solid periwinkle wilt medium (PWG) (Davis *et al.*, 1981) for 7 days at 28 °C. The bacterial suspension (10⁸ CFU mL⁻¹) was prepared in 1x PBS buffer for petiole inoculation on the first leaf of ten transgenic and wild-type (WT) plants, for both transgenic tobacco and citrus. One month after inoculation, genomic DNA was extracted from petioles of the first leaf above the inoculation point (aip), as previously described, and bacterial detection was performed by PCR using RST31/33 primers (Minsavage *et al.*, 1994). Only the *Xylella*-positive and mock-inoculated individuals were maintained for further analysis.

Transgenic citrus plants were evaluated regarding *X. fastidiosa* population 18 months after inoculation by qPCR in ABI PRISM 7500 Fast (Applied Biosystems). Petioles were collected in two different parts of the plants for total DNA extraction, at 5 and 30 cm aip. The quantification was performed using TaqMan PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) using primers CVC-1 and CCSM-1 and the probe TAQCVC (Table S1) and the bacterial population was calculated according to the standard curve developed for *X. fastidiosa* (Oliveira *et al.*, 2002). Infected plants were evaluated for the disease severity and scored by three inspectors using a diagrammatic scale (Caserta *et al.*, 2017).

Arabidopsis Col-0 and *efr-1* plants were infected with *Xff* as described in Pereira *et al.* (2019). Briefly, twelve six- to seven-week-old plants per genotype were inoculated

by dropping 5 μ L of bacterial inoculum or PBS buffer at the midrib. The petiole tissue under the drop was pricked seven to eight times using an insulin needle. After 14 days, petiole tissue below the infection point was harvested for DNA isolation and qPCR of the *HL* gene from *Xff* (Table S1).

Supplementary Material

Table S1 List of primers and probes used in this study.

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')
FMV_F	F- TGGCTTGTGGGGACCAGAC
35S_F	F- AGGAGCATCGTGGAAAAAGA
<i>EFR</i> _R	R- GAAGCTCACCTCCAAGTCTA
CVC-1	F- AGATGAAAACAATCATGCAAA
CCSM-1	R- GCGCATGCCAAGTCCATATTT
TAQCVC probe	(6FAM) AACCGCAGCAGAAGCCGCTCATC (TAMRA)p
<i>HL5</i> ¹	F- AAGGCAATAAACGCGCACTA
<i>HL6</i> ¹	R- GGTTTTGCTGACTGGCAACA
<i>EFR</i> _RTqPCR	F- TGGCTGCAGCTAGAAGATCTGG R- TGGCTGCAGCTAGAAGATCTGG
<i>Cyclophilin</i> _RTqPCR	F- AGAGTATGCAGAGGAATGG R- GTCCTTAACAGAAGTCCGT
<i>WRKY23</i> _RTqPCR	F- CTCCTCACTCATCTCAATCTC R- CTGCTGCTGTTGTTGTTGTT
<i>SGT1</i> _RTqPCR	F- AGGATGTTGAGACAGTGATGG R- CTCCTCAGGCTTCTGGTAAA
<i>NPR2</i> _RTqPCR	F- TCCTAGGATGGAAGCCCTTAT R- GGTCGTCCTCCATGAACTTATC
<i>EDS1</i> _RTqPCR	F- GGCTCGAGTATGCCCTGAAG R- CTTGCCAGAAACATGATTCC

¹ (Francis *et al.*, 2006)

Table S2 *Citrus* transformation assays performed in Valencia sweet orange for *EFR* gene transfer. Number of recovered plants and transformation efficiency are indicated.

Experiment	N° of explants	N° of shoots	GUS (+) shoots	PCR (+) plants/ Analyzed plants	Transformation efficiency (%)*
1	248	121	5	5/5	2.02
2	188	80	3	3/3	1.60
3	151	101	14	5/14	9.27
4	148	96	17	7/17	11.49

**gus* (+) shoots/total explants infected

Fig. S1 ROS burst in Col-0 and *efr-1* mutant after treatment with *Xff* (OD₆₀₀ 0.125) and with multiple elf peptides. **(a)** Total photon count represented as relative light units following PAMP treatment (n=10) and **(b)** ROS production in *Arabidopsis* (Col-0) triggered by elf18 peptides. Error bars represent standard error of the mean. Statistical differences are represented by asterisks and were calculated using a two-tailed *t*-test (* $p < 0.05$). The experiments were performed twice with similar results.

Fig. S2 Transgenic tobacco expressing *EFR*. **(a)** PCR confirmation of five transgenic lines showing the expected amplicon of 2403 bp (black arrow). L = 1Kb DNA ladder (Thermo Fisher Scientific), T1-T5 = transgenic lines, C+ = positive control (empty vector), C- = WT tobacco genomic DNA. **(b)** Relative expression profile of the *EFR* encoding gene in transgenic tobacco plants. RLU: relative unit of light. Values are means \pm standard error (SE) of at least six biological replicates. Statistical differences compared to WT were determined by the Student's *t* test (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$).

Fig. S3 Schematic representation of the expression cassette containing the *EFR* gene from *Arabidopsis* used for sweet orange *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation. The

neomycin phosphotransferase encoding sequence (*NptII*) used as the plant selection marker is under the control of the 35S promoter and terminator. The *gus* reporter gene expression is regulated by the ubiquitin (Ubi) promoter and the nopaline synthase (NOS) terminator. The *EFR* gene is under the control of the *fig mosaic virus* (*FMV*) promoter and the *octopine synthase* (*OCS*) terminator.

Fig. S4. Transgene copy number assessed by qPCR showing one copy per line. Quantification was performed using primers at the 35S promoter regulating *NptII* selection marker and the lipid transfer protein (LTP) gene. Pos Col: sweet-orange positive control with two copies confirmed by southern blot.

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